

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: Samer

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software:(word365 on Windows 10)

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO PROFESIONAL PAPER WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

EUCLID's ACA-401D period one is the first step in familiarising students with EUCLID's guidelines, templates and the use of Zotero. The course material of period one consists of a mixture of videos, study instructions, templates, sample papers and an extensive PDF file to guide students on precise academic paper writing. The first video aims to help students to understand the first five periods of the course. The purpose of the second video is to save time and effort for students by demonstrating how to use styles and format document in words. The course pack of period one consists of nine chapters on various subjects to help students with accurate academic essay writing. In the review paper, which follows each of the first five periods, students are expected to describe how the learning objectives have been met by means of the course material. Students should reflect on the course material and explain what they found to be new, practical, difficult, problematic and controversial.

2)STEP ONE: HOW TO CONVINCЕ READERS WITH YOUR IDEA(S)

The first chapter in the course pack is about essay writing. It starts by explaining the meaning of the thesis statement (EUCLID 2019, 1). This is a short statement (1-2 sentences) that summarises the main point or aim of the essay or research paper. It is developed, supported and explained in the text by means of examples and evidence (Rodborg 1999).

I have written and published scientific papers in the past, however, I did not follow a structured method in writing. I found the presented course material offers an organised system on planning, preparing and writing a proficient essay. Students must start the process of essay writing by reading and researching the subject with a purpose. This will enable students to analyse, understand the study question and to decide if the studied material can be used to support an argument. It is essential for students to take notes throughout the period of reading and researching as these notes will form the foundation of the essay (EUCLID 2019, 2).

At the writing phase of an essay, students need to draft an answer to the study question and decide on which evidence to use. Writing should be structured into an introduction, body and conclusion. This is to be followed by referencing, editing, proof reading and submitting the essay (EUCLID 2019, 3-4).

In the introduction section, students need to present the subject areas with a general broad opening and the focus the essay onto a specific area. Moreover, they will need to mention the thesis statement and answer the question along with supporting evidence.

The body of the essay will consist of structured paragraphs where students need to answer the questions and develop an argument. Furthermore, examples and reasons to support the argument declared in the introduction can be used in this section (EUCLID 2019, 3).

The conclusion part moves from specific to general. This is where students need to re-summarise the main points, re-state answers to questions and discuss possible implications along with future direction for research (University of Birmingham 2017).

I liked the concept of “road mapping” the essay before writing it (EUCLID 2019, 3). I studied the theories of concept and mind mapping when I did my postgraduate studies in medical education. People learn in different ways. The most common way for providing information is through reading. However, some people learn more efficiently via other techniques such as illustrating diagrams, using graphical presentations and visual learning. Concept mapping is a valuable method for allowing learning through a pictorial modality because it uses illustrations, charts, drafts and other visual depictions to generate and comprehend concepts (Safdar 2012).

The second concept, which I was pleased to see in the course resources, is the recommendation to adopt a balanced view and to embrace a variety of arguments and opposing evidence as all evidence will need to be observed (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Counterarguments are ideas that are opposite to your ideas. In an academic discussion you must show that you are familiar with both sides of the argument and provide reasons to support your position. It is usual to deal with the counterarguments first, before giving your view (Baily 2011).

3)STEP TWO: AVOID PIRACY AND QUOTE THE SOURCE OF THE INFORMATION

Presenting someone else's work or ideas as your own without acknowledgment to the author is known as plagiarism. This is applied to any kind of academic work like text, media, published and unpublished books or journals. Quotation without acknowledging is considered as a form of plagiarism. Quotations should be identified by using quotation marks or indentation. Paraphrasing is another form of plagiarism. Paraphrasing is accomplished by changing words or their order or following the same writing style without proper acknowledgement to the original author (EUCLID 2019, 5). Plagiarism is viewed as a kind of theft and is considered as a breach of academic honesty. Researchers and students must be transparent, and they must acknowledge the source of information to avoid plagiarism (University of Oxford n.d.).

I fully support EUCLID's strong stand on not accepting any form of plagiarism to maintain integrity and high academic standards (EUCLID 2019, 5).

4)STEP THREE: CHOOSE YOUR STYLE OF WRITING

“Writing, just like speaking, is simply a way to communicate with other people” (University of Greenwich 2016). Universities, journals and book publishers demand that academic work should be written in certain ways to ascertain coherence and consistency. For this reason, there are a variety of styles in citing and referencing used by different academic institutions and publishers. EUCLID recommends the use of Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognised Rules are also acceptable (EUCLID 2019, 24).

I have not used this style before, but I have done some research on it and found that Chicago (Turabian) Style is a method of formatting and referencing that was first published by the University of Chicago Press in 1906 (Boundless writing 2020). In 2010, the sixteenth edition of the Chicago Manual of Style was published. Turabian Style is the same as Chicago Style but it focuses on providing students with guidelines on writing papers, thesis and essays. Chicago/Turabian style offers authors a selection of many different formats. Moreover, it allows the mixing of formats, if the outcome is clear and consistent. The sixteenth edition of The Chicago Manual of Style permits the use of both in-text citation systems (Author–Date) or footnotes and endnotes depending on whether the paper has a complete bibliography at the end. In addition, Chicago (Turabian) Style contains several basic grammatical rules (Boundless writing 2020).

5) CONCLUSION

I believe that the course material in period one of the ACA-401D has covered a wide range of subjects starting with essay writing and focusing on good practice. The course material was thorough and clear. I enjoyed the delivery of the course material through visual and text modalities and found it very helpful. I was impressed with the structuring of essay writing suggested by the course material especially the recommendation of using balanced arguments and concept mapping. I still have problems with getting word to connect to Zotero, but I will do more research on it. I found the information in period one practical and not controversial.

In conclusion, I believe that the learning objectives of period one, which are to familiarise students with EUCLID's guidelines and templates, have been met by the means of the course material. Moreover, the course material has covered a wide range of topics, which will set up the foundation for future tasks.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D
Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.